

Deliverable 4.6: Sectoral Strategy Infographics

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Imprint

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Key messages

1. The infographics are based on the six MERLIN Sectoral Strategies which provide a roadmap for integrating Nature-based Solutions (NbS) into key economic sectors: Agriculture, Hydropower, Insurance, Navigation, Peat Extraction, and Water Supply and Sanitation.
2. Economic sectors play a crucial role in both impacting and benefiting from freshwater restoration. These strategies provide clear, actionable pathways for aligning Sectoral priorities with NbS implementation.
3. The infographics illustrate each sector's vision, core actions, and interpretation of NbS, making complex strategies more accessible and easier to distribute.
4. By presenting key concepts visually, the infographics invite non-academic audiences – policymakers, industry experts, and the public – to better engage with sector-specific approaches to NbS.

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the development and a collection of infographics designed to communicate key aspects of economic Sectoral strategies, prepared under the MERLIN project. The infographics are designed to communicate key aspects of economic Sectoral strategies and both the infographics and the strategies are available on MERLIN's website:

- Agriculture: [available here](#)
- Hydropower: [available here](#)
- Insurance: [available here](#)
- Navigation: [available here](#)
- Peat Extraction: [available here](#)
- Water Supply and Sanitation: [available here](#)

The infographics were created to publicise the Sectoral strategies to a **diverse audience**. They provide an accessible and visual summary of each sector's vision, core actions, and interpretation of Nature-based Solutions (NbS). The infographics are intended to help policymakers, industry experts, researchers, and the wider public engage with sector-specific approaches to NbS and read the full Strategy.

Given their influence, economic sectors - comprising various business interests - play a **crucial role** in advancing NbS and driving sustainable practices that support ecosystem restoration. Through tailored strategies and the integration of NbS, these sectors have the potential to contribute significantly to environmental and societal resilience.

These infographics focus on Sectoral action plans, outlining how industries can integrate NbS into their practices and policies. The vision and actions are often **strategic** and not necessarily connected to individual restoration measures or sites. However, the infographics have used the MERLIN landscape infographics ([available here](#)) to visually link the Sectoral visions and actions to their ecological and societal outcomes.

Introduction

This deliverable presents the set of sectoral strategy infographics developed under the MERLIN project as visual summaries of the six Sectoral Strategies – Agriculture, Hydropower, Insurance, Navigation, Peat Extraction, and Water Supply and Sanitation. Infographics are efficient and engaging tools for communication - they distill complex content into concise, visual formats, making key messages easier to grasp, compare, and share. This is why they were chosen to complement the Sectoral Strategies. Their primary purpose is to support dissemination, and they also offer an accessible entry point into sector-specific approaches to Nature-based Solutions (NbS), helping to engage a wider audience beyond traditional policy and academic circles.

The following sections present the methodology behind the development of the infographics, followed by the six sector-specific visuals. Each infographic includes a summary of the sector's vision, its interpretation of NbS, and the key actions—along with relevant actors, timelines, or governance levels, where applicable. A QR code is also included to provide direct access to the full Sectoral Strategy. The final section outlines the next steps for the deliverable, including suggestions for how the infographics can be used, adapted, and disseminated in future communication and engagement activities.

Methodology

The development of the Sectoral infographics followed a **structured, iterative process** to ensure they effectively communicate key aspects of each Sectoral Strategy. The infographics were not fully standardised, as they needed to reflect the different messages in the strategies and the different audiences and, therefore, reflect the different results of the iterations.

Since 2021, MERLIN has actively collaborated with the six economic sectors through roundtables, interviews, written feedback, and continuous dialogue. These interactions helped establish Sectoral **Communities of Practice** (CoPs), fostering knowledge sharing and collaboration. The strategies outlined in [Deliverable D4.5](#) both shape and support these CoPs, highlighting how sectors can actively contribute to safeguarding Europe's freshwater resources while benefiting from the transformation.

The development of the infographics was closely integrated with the refinement of **Sectoral Strategies**. As a first step, Sectoral teams were asked to propose visual representations of their draft Strategies. These early sketches were discussed both internally and with the respective CoPs. Based on this input, the design team (from the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, and the Schnee auf Moss Advertising Agency) developed a more standardised visual format.

This was followed by several **rounds of feedback** from Sectoral teams, Work Package coordinators, and the project coordination team to define a shared content structure - including common elements such as the vision, the Sector's understanding of NbS, and the key actions - while still allowing flexibility to reflect the specificities of each Sector.

In the final phase, elements of the strategic and conceptual design were aligned with MERLIN's landscape-level infographics to provide visual grounding for the actions and Sectoral visions. A final round of edits aimed to make the language concise but not misleading - particularly in Sectors where there was considerable delicacy needed to convey the Sectoral roles and responsibilities.

1. Agriculture

Agriculture Sectoral Strategy

Read the strategy here →

- Action A** Engaging and assisting farmers to adopt NbS to raise awareness of the present status of ecosystems and of possible methodologies and pathways to implementing NbS measures.
- Action B** Sharing knowledge of NbS benefits to mobilise public support for policy and other changes needed to mainstream NbS.
- Action C** Reforming the current European policy framework to rebalance CAP policy to deliver more NbS, level up environmental outcomes with existing regulations, broaden the factors included in cost-benefit decisions.
- Action D** Initiate landscape partnerships for multi-stakeholders coordinated NbS implementation to incorporate diverse perspectives, enhance collaboration and the sustainability of the interventions.
- Action E** Accelerating relevant innovations to support the prioritisation of new agricultural production systems, products, technologies and related services.
- Action F** Strengthening market and financing mechanisms that reward NbS in farming to increase resources for the investments and capacity-building needed for the transition to sustainable farming systems.

NbS in this context

- Interventions on agricultural lands that benefit agricultural practises and improve freshwater ecosystems to increase the provision of multiple ecosystem services.
- Increase resource use efficiency to cut pollutant emissions and reduce water abstraction.
- Optimize soil, crop, and livestock management to enhance soil functions, nutrient cycling, and water retention.
- Restore catchment hydrology to support nutrient recycling, pollutant breakdown, and water storage.

Relevant spatial scales

- The NbS are implemented at:
- Field and farm
 - Stream (sub-catchment)
 - Floodplains (large catchments)

NbS – Nature-based Solutions

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2. Hydropower

Hydropower Sector Strategy

Involving the Hydropower Sector in strategic barrier removal: applying an NbS approach

Read the strategy here →

E
Action

Provide Sector specific tools to design NbS programmes with barrier removal

A
Action

Increase understanding of an NbS approach to barrier removal

B
Action

Highlight synergies between energy/ climate change and nature restoration policies

2030 Vision

- Barrier removal and NbS approach embedded in company strategies
- Works in partnership to remove barriers
- Has the relevant skills and expertise for ambitious action

NbS in this context

Strategic removal of transversal barriers with no economic value to benefit the Hydropower Sector.

D
Action

Build Sector capacity for leadership and collaboration

C
Action

Develop finance pathways guided by an NbS approach

NbS – Nature-based Solutions

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3. Insurance

Insurance Sector Strategy

Read the strategy here →

Vision
 The European insurance sector promotes the use of large-scale freshwater NbS as water-related disaster risk reduction and ecosystem-based adaptation measures.

Action 1 (supporting)
 Sharing of loss data

Action 2 (supporting)
 Analysis of NbS cost-benefits

Action 3
 Development of standards or tools

Action 4
 Leveraging policies as enablers

Action 5 (supporting)
 Revision of insurance portfolios

Action 6
 Creation of innovative products and services

Action 7
 Investment in restoration actions

NbS in this context
 Freshwater restoration enhancing the regulation function of ecosystems to reduce disaster and climate-related risks
 NbS – Nature-based Solutions

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4. Navigation

Navigation Sector Strategy

Read the strategy here →

International
National
Regional

2030

2050

2035

Vision

Greening the European inland waterway network by mainstreaming Nature-based Solutions

Action A

Develop an action plan for greening inland waterways

Actors: DG Move, DG Env

Action B

Build confidence by installing Communities of Practice

Actors: DG Move, DG Env, international river basin commissions, national and regional waterway authorities

Action C

Share experiences with NbS in inland waterways

Actors: Stakeholders in NbS implementation projects

Action D

Minimise engineering of inland waterways

Actors: Waterway authorities and nature organisations

Action E

Prioritise inland waterways based on their ecological status and role for navigation

Actors: DG Move and DG Env with contributions from national authorities responsible for implementing TEN-T, WFD and NRL

NbS in this context

Measures that serve the navigability of inland waterways while improving their ecological status, particularly river hydromorphology. This includes measures that mitigate the effects of climate change on inland waterways.

NbS – Nature-based Solutions

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5. Peat Extraction

6. Water Supply and Sanitation

Water Supply and Sanitation Sector Strategy

Read the strategy here →

NbS in this context

Large-scale measures that aim to improve water quality, enhance ecological health, and support sustainable water cycles.

NbS – Nature-based Solutions

Vision

- Widespread understanding and integration of NbS in the water sector
- Clear and accessible evidence on the value of NbS
- Mainstreaming NbS in policy and practice

Challenge 1

The 'engineering culture' of water operators

Action A

Boosting awareness and integration of NbS in the Water Supply and Sanitation Sector

Challenge 2

The lack of consolidated metrics for evaluating the effectiveness of NbS in comparison to traditional 'grey' solutions

Action C

Mainstreaming NbS in EU and national policies and coordination frameworks

Challenge 3

The complex governance of NbS

Action B

Streamlining methodologies supporting decision-making on NbS through communities of practice and better integration in project evaluation

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Next steps

The Sectoral Strategy infographics play a key role in **disseminating** the strategies and making them **accessible** to a broad audience. As visual summaries, they provide an engaging and easy-to-digest entry point into Sectoral approaches to NbS, serving as valuable tools for outreach and communication. Ensuring their visibility on the MERLIN website will help different stakeholders and audiences quickly grasp the key takeaways from each Strategy.

Beyond the website, the infographics can be **integrated** into presentations, workshops, and policy briefings, facilitating discussions with Sector representatives. They also offer support for stakeholder engagement activities at conferences and sector-specific events, ensuring that NbS strategies reach the right audiences effectively.

National MERLIN Days also offer valuable opportunities to further disseminate the Sectoral infographics, including through potential translations to enhance accessibility for national audiences. Additionally, sectoral teams are planning targeted dissemination activities. For example, the Hydropower team will present at the European Climate Change Conference in June 2025, the Water Supply and Sanitation team is preparing an NbS-focused event for the summer of 2025, and the Peat Extraction team will present at the annual conference of the International Peatland Society (IPS) in June 2025.

Finally, by combining the two approaches of Sectoral action plans and landscape-focused strategies, we can create a more integrated vision for freshwater restoration. Therefore, a **cross-sectoral routemap infographic** is planned to foster greater coherence and collaboration in NbS implementation.